

Abundances of CNO in candidate young metal-poor stars

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Abstract

In this contribution we investigate the CNO abundances in five apparently young evolved stars, with the aim of discriminating between truly young stars and stars that were rejuvenated by accreting mass from another star. Stars that have accreted mass are expected to show low C and O and a very low [C/O] ratio, as displayed by some stars in the Globular Cluster 47 Tuc, that are believed to have undergone mass-transfer. In our sample the low [C/O] ratios observed appear to be compatible with their evolutionary status. There is thus no indication for these stars having accreted mass.

1 Introduction

In the last years several metal-poor stars that are apparently young have been discovered (see e.g. Caffau et al. 2020, 2024; Bonifacio et al. 2021). Some of these could be young stars that were formed as a consequence of a starburst induced in a gas rich dwarf galaxy infalling into the Milky Way, as suggested by Yang et al. (2024). Others could be stars that have been rejuvenated by accreting mass from one or several other stars. A possible diagnostic to discriminate the two cases is the [C/O] ratio.

Table 1: Parameters of the program stars

Gaia DR3 ID	NAME	Teff K	log g log(cgs)	VTURB kms ⁻¹	[Fe/H] dex	S/N@420 nm	Vrad kms ⁻¹
3151624328675371264	YMP015	4910	2.38	1.48	-0.67	46	26.2
2716352208089611264	YMP033	4600	1.00	2.06	-1.67	70	-260.1
6897294199759073536	YMP053	5229	2.43	1.68	-1.47	72	-70.3
2796582811359131392	YMP054	5151	2.10	1.84	-2.00	94	-157.2
722021080910867584	YMP067	4546	0.65	2.26	-2.41	80	-13.0

2 Target selection and observations

In the Gaia DR3, we selected a sample of bright stars ($7 \leq G \leq 13$) with transverse velocity in excess of 500 kms⁻¹, parallax larger than three times the parallax error. Among these stars we noticed a large number of stars, that, in the colour-magnitude diagram, occupy the region where young evolved stars can be found (see Bonifacio et al. 2024, figures 1 and 2).

A subset of these stars was observed with UVES at the ESO 8.2 m telescope with the DIC2 437+760 setting, that covers the wavelength ranges 373—499 nm and 565—946 nm using a 0".5 slit that provides a resolving power of about 75 000 in the blue and 70 000 in the red arm.

In our contribution to this conference we shall discuss the CNO abundances of five apparently young stars whose characteristics are reported in Table 1.

2.1 Stellar parameters and chemical abundances

We used the Gaia photometry, corrected for reddening according to the maps of Vergely et al. (2022) and extinction coefficients from the KOALA database (Mucciarelli et al. 2025) to determine effective temperatures. The photogeometric distances of Bailer-Jones et al. (2021) were used with the Stefan-Boltzmann equation to determine surface gravities. The whole procedure was iterative as described in detail by Lombardo et al. (2021), with one difference: at each step we estimated ages and masses using the Bayesian inference code SPInS (Lebreton & Reese 2020; Reese & Lebreton 2020) and the assumed mass was updated. Only three iterations were necessary to converge, with variations of effective temperatures being less than 10 K and in surface gravity of less than 0.05 dex. To run SPInS we used the BaSTI evolutionary tracks enhanced in α elements by 0.4 dex (Pietrinferni et al. 2021). We adopted a flat prior of ages between 0 and 13.8 Gyr to avoid ages larger than the age of the Universe.

At each iteration we run MyGIsFOS (Sbordone et al. 2014) to determine the chemical composition of each star. The oxygen abundances were determined by MyGIsFOS using at least one [OI] line (630.0 nm, 636.3 nm) and at least one permitted O I line of the IR triplet (777.1 nm, 777.3 nm, 777.5 nm). Unsurprisingly it was for the warmest star of the sample YMP054 that we kept only two lines: the [OI] 630.0 nm with an equivalent width of 0.714 pm and the O I 777.1 nm line with an equivalent width of 1.342 pm. For the other four stars we have either five or four O I lines. When there were NLTE corrections for the triplet lines by Sitnova et al. (2013) we applied them to the LTE abundances derived by MyGIsFOS. If there were no corrections available at parameters near those of the stars we assumed a zero NLTE correction. The largest root mean square deviation among the O I lines is found for YMP067, 0.12 dex, over five lines, and for this star we did not apply any NLTE corrections.

For carbon MyGIsFOS determined the abundance from one or more of the IR C I lines at 833.5149 nm,

Table 2: CNO abundances for our program stars

Star	A(O)	$\sigma[A(O)]$	N_O	A(C) _{CI}	A(C) _{CH}	A(N) _{388_CI}	A(N) _{388_CH}	A(N) _{421_CH}
YMP015	8.36	0.03	5	7.81	7.70		7.30	7.60
YMP033	7.64	0.06	4	6.49	6.28		6.75	
YMP053	7.91	0.04	4	7.21	6.73	7.20	6.71	
YMP054	7.31	0.004	2	6.61	6.57	6.22 ^a	6.22 ^a	
YMP067	7.10	0.12	5		5.54		6.37	

We assumed A(C) 6.52, that is the average of the abundance from C I and CH.

872.7126 nm, 906.1432 and 907.8278 nm. The C I lines used were: for YMP015 the lines at 833.5 and 872.7 nm; for YMP033 the line at 906.1 nm; for YMP053 the lines at 872.7 and 907.8 nm; for YMP054 the lines at 833.5 and 906.1 nm; for YMP067 no line. For all stars we determined the C abundance also from a χ^2 fit to the CH $A^2\Delta - X^2\Pi$ molecular band, hereafter the G-band (Fraunhofer 1817). For all stars, except YMP054, the C abundance from the G-band is significantly lower than that determined from the atomic lines. We do not have at our disposal NLTE computations for the IR carbon lines that cover the stellar parameters of the present sample. However computations of Alexeeva et al. (2014) suggest there should not be a large NLTE effect, of the order of -0.1 dex. Bonifacio et al. (2025) pointed out the case of three extremely-metal poor stars, G 64-12, G 64-37 and G 275-4, for which a disturbing discrepancy exists between the carbon abundances derived from the atomic lines, even with the most sophisticated 3D NLTE modelling and the G-band. We are here in a much higher metallicity regime, but the underlying reason could be the same. A suspected reason are 3D NLTE effects on one or several of the diatomic molecules that are linked to CH through the chemical network: CH, CO, NH, OH, CN.

Considering the wavelength range available to us the only possibility to determine the nitrogen abundance is through the CN $B^2\Sigma^+ - X^2\Sigma^+(0-0)$ band at 388.4 nm and through the CN $B^2\Sigma^+ - X^2\Sigma^+(0-1)$ band at 421.6 nm. The difficulty in modelling the 388.3 nm band, affected both by 3D and NLTE effects (Bonifacio et al. 2013; Mount & Linsky 1975) is well known, and because of lack of investigations, we do not know if the 421.6 nm band is any better. In our sample the 421.6 nm band is detectable only in YMP015 and YMP033, in all cases there is a considerable discrepancy. Furthermore for the stars for which we had a discrepancy in the C abundances from atomic line and G-band we computed the N abundance for both possible C abundances. We note that all our fits to the CN 388 nm are poor, we are able to reproduce the wings of the band, but not the core. If we force the fit to the core, we lose the wings. This same problem was found by Spite et al. (2005), suggesting that our model atmospheres and line transfer computations are not adequate to fully describe this band. The usual suspects are a chromospheric emission in the core and 3D-NLTE effects. Our results for the CNO elements are summarised in Table 2

3 Discussion and conclusions

From the kinematics our targets appear to belong to the halo, except, YMP015 that is a thick disc stars. They all appear to be too young with respect to their kinematical classification (Bonifacio et al. in prep). They could be either truly young stars or evolved blue straggler stars (BSS).

In this contribution we investigate the CNO abundances in these stars to see if they can help to discriminate between BSS and young stars. Ferraro et al. (2006) found among the BSS in the Galactic Globular Cluster (GGC) 47 Tuc a group of stars that are strongly depleted in C and O and their are shown in our Fig. 1. They interpret

Figure 1: The [O/Fe] vs. [C/Fe] diagram for our stars. As reference stars we use the BSS stars in 47 Tuc from (Ferraro et al. 2006, black, open symbols collisional BSS, filled symbols mass transfer BSS) and from the MINCE collaboration (Lombardo et al., these proceedings, cyan symbols).

Figure 2: The $[N/Fe]$ vs. $[C/Fe]$ diagram for our program stars. As reference samples we took the Large Programme (LP) stars of Spite et al. (2005), mixed (open black symbols) and not mixed (filled black symbols) and also the N abundances derived from the 388 nm CN band (violet \times symbols), and the MINCE collaboration giants (Lombardo et al. these proceedings, cyan symbols).

these stars as BSS formed through mass transfer, since an extra mixing is expected to occur in this case (Sarna & De Greve 1996). The other BSS that are not strongly depleted in C and O are interpreted as having been formed through collisions, since in this process no extensive mixing is expected (Lombardi et al. 1995). In GGC the majority of BSS is expected to be formed through collisions and, for example, C and O depleted BSS have been found in the M 30 (Lovisi et al. 2013b), but not in NGC 6752 (Lovisi et al. 2013a). Among field stars, however we expect the majority of BSS to be formed by mass transfer (Preston & Sneden 2000) because stellar collisions are exceedingly rare. If our stars were BSS we should expect them to be from mass transfer, so heavily depleted in C and O, which is clearly not the case, as shown in Fig. 1. One complication is that our stars are evolved and Ferraro et al. (2006) suggested that these depletions may be temporary and as the BSS evolves the mixing restores the original abundances, prior to the mass transfer. Ferraro et al. (2006), however, do not corroborate this suggestion with any theoretical or observational evidence. In our case we note that the mass transferred must be very large, in the range 0.2 to 0.5 M_{\odot} , assuming the accreting star has a mass of 0.8 M_{\odot} , even larger if its mass is smaller. Therefore we are not talking about a thin layer that only pollutes the stellar photosphere.

Since we have the abundances of C, N and O, we can try to assess the mixing properties of our stars. In Fig. 2 we plot the [N/Fe] vs. [C/Fe] diagram for our program stars with two comparison samples, the MINCE sample (Lombardo et al. these proceedings) and the ESO Large Programme “First Stars” (Spite et al. 2005, hereafter LP). The MINCE sample has metallicities similar to our sample, but their nitrogen abundances were derived from the NH $A^3\Pi_i - X^3\Sigma^-$ band at 336 nm. The LP is typically more metal-poor than our sample, all their N abundances are also derived from the same UV NH band (black symbols), however for a subset of stars they also determined N abundances from the 388 nm band, like us. Among the LP stars one sees discrepancies between the NH and CN bands, in both directions. From this plot it is clear that YMP015, YMP033, YMP053 and YMP067 qualify as mixed stars, while YMP054 is not mixed. The comparison with the MINCE sample, that occupies the same region in the diagram, suggests that probably the abundances derived from NH and CN are consistent. Any discrepancies should not change the classification of the star as mixed or not mixed. Our interpretation is that the carbon deficiencies and nitrogen enhancement in these stars are compatible with their evolutionary status and can be explained by mixing.

Our conclusion is that although we cannot exclude that these stars are evolved BSS, the abundances of CNO point towards their being truly young. It is clear that the sample may contain both kinds of stars. Wider searches are needed, especially aimed at finding more of these metal poor apparently young stars and especially of higher masses. If a significant number stars with masses exceeding 1.6 M_{\odot} were selected, then it would be very difficult to explain them as evolved BSS.

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